

Enhancement of Soft and Hard Tissue Structures Through Bone Regenerative Therapies in Periodontal Disease: A Comprehensive Review

Author

Shivani Koli, *(BDS) Department of Periodontics and Implantology, Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College & Research Centre, Nagpur, India*

Co-Authors

Corresponding Author:

Surekha Rathod*, *[MDS] Department of Periodontics and Implantology, Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College & Research Centre, Nagpur, India*

Abhay Kolte, *[MDS] Department of Periodontics and Implantology, Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College & Research Centre, Nagpur, India.*

Abstract

Chronic periodontitis is a complex inflammatory condition that leads to the gradual deterioration of periodontal tissues, such as the gingiva, periodontal ligament, and alveolar bone. The disease pathogenesis involves complex interactions between microbial, host, genetic, and environmental factors, with subgingival biofilms playing a key role. Host modulation therapies (HMTs), including local drug delivery (LDD) systems, have emerged as promising adjunctive treatments. Alendronate, statins, and metformin, when delivered locally, have shown potential in enhancing periodontal regeneration, reducing inflammation, and preventing bone loss. Alendronate inhibits osteoclast activity, promoting bone preservation and improving graft integration. Statins exert antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and osteogenic effects, enhancing clinical attachment levels and reducing bone resorption. Metformin, through activation of AMPK, improves bone formation, reduces oxidative stress, and accelerates healing, particularly in diabetic conditions. Several studies have demonstrated the efficacy of these agents, with notable enhancement in radiographic defect fill, clinical attachment level, and probing depth. These findings highlight the potential of LDD systems in advancing periodontal disease management.

Keywords- alendronate, metformin, statins, chronic periodontitis, bone fill

I. Introduction and Background

Periodontitis, a multifactorial inflammatory disease affecting the periodontium, primarily involves the deterioration of tooth-supporting structures such as the gingiva, periodontal ligament, and alveolar bone. Clinically, it manifests as clinical attachment loss, formation of periodontal pockets, and resorption of alveolar bone, which, if left untreated, can eventually result in tooth loss.^[1]

The development of chronic periodontitis involves an intricate interaction between microbial, host, genetic, and environmental factors. Subgingival biofilms, predominantly composed of dysbiotic microbial communities, are the primary etiological agents. However, host factors, such as a dysregulated immune-inflammatory response, play a critical role in tissue destruction. Understanding these intricate host-microbe interactions has paved the way for targeted therapeutic strategies, including host modulation therapies (HMTs), which aim to balance the inflammatory response and prevent tissue damage.^[2,3]

Local drug delivery (LDD) systems offer a targeted approach to treating periodontal disease, improving the efficacy of antimicrobial agents such as alendronate, statins, and metformin. By applying these drugs directly to periodontal pockets, LDD allows for higher concentrations of the active agents at the site of disease, minimizing systemic side effects and enhancing the therapeutic outcomes in managing periodontitis.^[4]

Anti-inflammatory agents like alendronate, statins, and metformin offer promising adjunctive therapies in periodontal disease management by altering the immunological response of the host, reducing inflammation, and potentially preventing tissue damage and bone loss associated with periodontitis.

II. Comprehensive Overview of Alendronate, Statins, and Metformin as Local Drug Delivery Agents in Periodontal Disease

	ALENDRONATE ^[5]	STATINS ^[11]	METFORMIN ^[15]
CHEMICAL STRUCTURE			
Pharmacological properties	Inhibits geranylgeranyl pyrophosphate (GGPP) production, reducing osteoclast activity and bone resorption ^[6] (Figure 1)	Inhibits HMG-CoA reductase, reducing cholesterol and promoting bone health. ^[12] (Figure 1)	Activates AMPK, enhancing glucose metabolism and osteogenesis.
Vascular Effects	Decreases vascular calcification, improving bone-vascular interactions ^[7] (Figure 2)	Improves endothelial function and reduces oxidative stress. ^[12]	Lowers cardiovascular risks like lipid levels and blood pressure.

Immune Modulation	Regulates monocyte/macrophage activity to control bone resorption. ^[8]	Modulates T-cell activation and cytokine production, enhancing immune response. ^[13]	Modulates T-cell activation and cytokine production, enhancing immune response.
Bone Effects	Preserves microarchitecture and increases trabecular thickness. ^[9]	Promotes osteoblast differentiation and new bone formation. ^[11]	Enhances osteogenesis via AMPK/MAPK signaling and supports bone remodeling.
Periodontal Applications	Prevents alveolar bone loss, reduces probing depth, and enhances graft integration. ^[10]	Improves clinical attachment levels and has antibacterial properties. ^[12]	Promotes bone regeneration, reduces oxidative stress, and accelerates healing.
Dental Implants	Enhances osseointegration and prevents peri-implant bone resorption. ^[2]	Promotes osseointegration by encouraging the formation of new bone surrounding the implant at the bone-implant interface. ^[14]	Supports osseointegration and reduces bacterial load around implants.
Adverse Effects	Risk of GI irritation, hypocalcemia, osteonecrosis of the jaw, and rare atypical fractures. ^[6]	Myalgia, rhabdomyolysis, and rare liver/kidney toxicity with prolonged use. ^[11]	GI discomfort, rare lactic acidosis, and potential B12 deficiency. ^[16]

(III) How Bone Regenerative Materials work in Chronic Periodontitis

Mechanism of Action of Alendronate ^[17]	Details
1. Binding to Bone	Strong affinity for hydroxyapatite crystals.
2. Inhibiting Osteoclast Activity	Disrupts mevalonate pathway, induces apoptosis. (Figure 1)
3. Promoting Osteoblast Function	Enhances activity, reduces apoptosis.
4. Anti-Inflammatory Effects	Reduces cytokines, MMPs, and prostaglandins.

Mechanism of action of Statins ^[12]	Details
1. Bone Resorption Inhibition	Blocks isoprenoid production, disrupting osteoclast function and reducing bone resorption. (Figure 2)
2. Bone Formation Promotion	Enhances osteoblast activity via BMP-2 and VEGF, while inhibiting osteoclastogenesis.
3. Antimicrobial Activity	Inhibits periodontal pathogens and disrupts biofilm stability, reducing bacterial pathogenicity.
4. Antioxidant & Angiogenesis	Prevents oxidative stress by inhibiting LDL oxidation and promotes angiogenesis via VEGF expression.

Mechanism of action of Metformin	Details
1. Bone Formation Enhancement	Activates AMPK and ERK pathways, stimulating osteoblast differentiation, type I collagen production, and angiogenesis. ^[18] (Figure 2)
2. Bone Resorption Reduction	Regulates RANKL/OPG ratio, suppresses Advanced Glycation End Products Receptor for Advanced Glycation End Products (AGEs-RAGE) interaction, and reduces alveolar bone loss in periodontitis. ^[18]
3. Anti-Inflammatory & Antibacterial	Suppresses NLRP3 inflammasome, modulates NF-kB, and reduces cytokine production, lowering inflammation and bone loss. ^[19]
4. Osseointegration Improvement	Promotes osteoblast proliferation, mineralization, and new bone formation around implants, enhancing stability and survival. ^[19]
5. Regenerative Effects	Enhances osteogenic differentiation in Dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs) via AMPK, aiding in bone repair, especially in diabetic conditions. ^[19]

Fig. 1 Role of Statins and Bisphosphonates in the Mevalonate Pathway: Mechanisms Targeting Osteoclast Survival and Function

Fig. 2 Role of Alendronate, Statins, and Metformin in Modulating Bone Resorption and Tissue Breakdown

IV. Studies which did support effect of these drugs in Chronic Periodontitis

Several studies have investigated the effectiveness of local drug delivery agents, such as metformin (MF), alendronate (ALN), and statins, in treating periodontal defects.

Metformin (1% gel) as a standalone treatment also led to greater PD reduction and CAL gain in chronic periodontitis (Pradeep et al., 2017).^[20]

Additionally, studies like those by Chen et al. (2016)^[21] and Akram et al. (2018)^[22] confirmed the effectiveness of alendronate in combination with scaling and root planing.

This studies highlighted the positive effects of local drug delivery systems in promoting periodontal regeneration and improving bone fill.

Authors	Title	Major outcome
A R Pradeep et al (2016) ^[23]	Comparative evaluation of subgingivally delivered 1% alendronate versus 1.2% atorvastatin gel in treatment of chronic periodontitis: a randomized placebo-controlled clinical trial	Local delivery of 1% ALN shows significantly greater improvements in PD, CAL, IBD depth, and (Defect depth Reduction) DDR%.
A R Pradeep et al (2016) ^[24]	1.2% Rosuvastatin Versus 1.2% Atorvastatin Gel Local Drug Delivery and Re-Delivery in Treatment of Intra-bony Defects in Chronic Periodontitis: A Randomized Placebo Controlled Clinical Trial	Greater probing depth reductions, gain in CAL, and DDR, with Rosuvastatin outperforming Atorvastatin and placebo.
A R Pradeep et al (2016) ^[25]	1.2% Rosuvastatin and 1.2% Atorvastatin Gel Local Drug Delivery and Redelivery in the Treatment of Class II Furcation Defects: A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial	Significant improvement in PD reduction, RVCAL, RHCAL and greater DDR%.
Chen et al (2016) ^[21]	Effectiveness of alendronate as an adjunct to scaling and root planing in the treatment of periodontitis: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled clinical trials	Decreased PD, gain in CAL and improved bone fill.
A R Pradeep et al (2017) ^[20]	Efficacy of 1% Metformin Gel in Moderate And Severe Chronic Periodontitis Subjects: A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial	Greater reduction in PD, gain in CAL, and reduction in IBD depth.
Ipshita et al (2018) ^[26]	One percent alendronate and aloe vera gel local host modulating agents in chronic periodontitis patients with class II furcation defects: A randomized, controlled clinical trial	1% ALN showed significant improvement in PPD, relative HCAL, VCAL and greater defect depth reduction.
Dileep P et al (2018) ^[27]	Comparative evaluation of subgingivally delivered 1.2% rosuvastatin and 1% metformin gel in treatment of intra-bony defects in chronic periodontitis: a randomized controlled clinical trial.	Marked reduction in PD, improvement in CAL, and increased bone fill.

Z. Akram et al (2018) ^[22]	Locally delivered metformin as adjunct to scaling and root planing in the treatment of periodontal defects: A systematic review and meta-analysis	Reduced PD, gain in CAL and effective in BD fill.
Mayssam et al (2019) ^[28]	Mandibular Degree II Furcation Defect Treatment With 1%Alendronate Gel Alone or In Combination with Platelet Rich Fibrin	Access therapy + 1% ALN + PRF showed marked reductions in PPD, along with improvements in RVAL, RHAL, and defect depth reduction.
Vidushi et al (2019) ^[29]	The comparative evaluation of 1% alendronate gel as local drug delivery system in chronic periodontitis in smokers and non smokers: Randomized clinical trial	LDD with 1% ALN showed substantial decrease in PD and improvement in CAL with significant gain in alveolar crest height and defect fill.
Chatterjee et al (2019) ^[30]	Efficacy of Locally Administered 1.2% Rosuvastatin Gel in Patients with Periodontitis: A Randomized Placebo Controlled Clinical Trial	significantly greater improvement in CAL, PD reduction and improved bone fill.
Dalia et al (2021) ^[31]	Evaluation of the Efficacy of 1% Alendronate Gel as Adjunctive Treatment in Class II Furcation Defects (Clinical, Radiographic and Biochemical Study)	Significant improvements in CAL, HPD and VPD, bone density, and RANKL levels at 6 months.
Rameshwari et al (2021) ^[32]	Clinical and radiographic comparison of 0.05% zoledronate gel (zometa) ® and 1% alendronate gel (fosamax) ® as a local drug delivery in the treatment of chronic periodontitis- a split mouth study	Both Alendronate and Zoledronate exhibited a decrease in plaque index, gingival index, and PPD, along with an increase in CAL and bone fill.
Cecoro et al (2021) ^[33]	Efficacy of locally delivered statins as an adjunct to scaling and root planing in the treatment of periodontitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Significant improvement in PD reduction and CAL gain.
Nitesh et al (2022) ^[34]	Comparative Evaluation of Efficacy of 1.2% ATV Gel and 1 % ALN Gel as Local Drug Delivery for the Treatment of Intrabony Defect in Individuals with Chronic Periodontitis – A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial	Both 1.2% ATV and 1% ALN gels were equally effective as LDD agents in intrabony defects, showing reductions in PD, improvements in CAL gain, and bone fill.
Arena et al (2022) ^[35]	Added effect of 1% topical alendronate in intra-bony and inter-radicular defects as part of step II periodontal therapy: a systematic review with meta-analysis and trial sequential analysis	Improved PD, CAL and bone defect depth.
Dipika et al (2023) ^[36]	Comparative Study between 1% Metformin and 1% Alendronate Gel in the Treatment of Infrabony Defects: A Randomized Controlled Trial	Both 1% MF and 1% ALN showed significant PD reduction, DDR, and RAL gain.

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